

What Is It (not) Like to Be a Bat

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

What Is It (not) Like to Be a Bat? is a contemporary interpretation of “What Is It Like to Be a Bat,” a 1974 paper by the American philosopher Thomas Nagel [1]. A self-built headset (Fig. 1), the work consists of three ultrasonic sensors and a gyroscope, which translate real-time data into sound — analogous to the sonar of a bat — creating an interactive musical “Bat-Theme”. It questions not only the hard problem of consciousness and the line between subjectivity and intersubjectivity but also the urge in the field of science, philosophy and technology to solve it, which might be impossible by nature.

Fig. 1. The Bat-Headset.

2. BACKGROUND & IDEA

Recent developments in philosophy, technology, and science have significantly diversified our understanding of consciousness and its implications. Within this discourse, materialists propose that all aspects of nature, including consciousness can be understood in terms of material configurations. This materialist perspective underpins the belief that consciousness can be replicated or transferred, exemplified by ideas such as mind uploading onto digital platforms or the creation of artificial consciousness.

However, this artistic work, inspired by Nagel's paper "What Is It Like to Be a Bat?" serves as a reminder and extension of an important argument. In Nagel's definition, an organism has consciousness if there is "something that it is like" to be that organism [1]. In other words, an organism is conscious if it has a subjective experience. But how can we ascertain if, for example, an artificial intelligence has a mental state? It might claim to have one, but could this not merely be the result of deterministic calculations in non-living matter? The real answer is: we may never truly know.

Nagel uses a bat as an example, a creature that, albeit a mammal like us, possesses a radically different sensory world. It navigates via sonar, sleeps upside down, and has a magnetic sense—experiences far removed from our own. Our attempts to imagine being a bat are constrained by not only the limits of our subjectivity but also anthropocentrism. Even if we were to transform into a bat, we would carry the remnants of our human life, unable to fully grasp the bat's experience. Science can teach us about a bat's neural structures and behavior, yet we cannot access the subjective experience of their sonar sensations.

Motivated by these reflections, I embarked on creating a headset that could extend our senses, allowing us to locate things in space using sonar like bats. The goal was not just to replicate a bat's navigation technique but to create a platform for artistic and subjective interpretations of this experience. This led to the development of *What Is It (not) Like to Be a Bat?*, a project that invites users to engage with these philosophical questions in a tangible way that embodies the tension between the opacity of subjective experience and the urge to render it transparent.

Fig. 2. The Bat-Headset from the back

3. TECHNICAL & ARTISTICAL REALIZATION

Technically, the artwork consists of a Bela, a Linux-based computer, three ultrasonic sensors (URM09), a 9 DoF gyroscope (BNO055), and a battery pack (2000mAh). The ultrasonic sensors are placed on the front and sides of the headset, while the gyroscope, battery pack and Bela are placed on the back (Fig. 2). The headset is self-sufficient in the sense that it does all of its processing and sound generation inside. The battery lasts for about 2-3 hours of use. Except for a script to translate the gyroscope data into OSC (open sound control) messages, everything is processed inside SuperCollider (SC).

Visually, the work consists of bat-like glasses and a rubber band with plexi glass plates, holding the technical components, which functions as a headband. The respective electronic parts are distributed around the entire headset, exposing its circuits and cables to the audience. Whereas the side ultrasonic sensors are laying inside custom 3D printed temples, and the front sensor attached to the mask.

I have chosen the bat-like glasses to express the absurd and presumptuous idea of being able to fully decipher and access consciousness through technology and science, which follow the pathos of empiricism and objectivity, in conflict with the inherent subjectivity of the way life presents us. However, I do acknowledge the progress and insight we gained through these disciplines. The design of the open circuit was meant to emphasize this naivety and add a playful element, as the whole work is meant to be a provocative interpretation of a bat experience that is inaccessible and therefore unprovable.

The composition generated in the headset depends on the input data from the sensors. The music thus serves not only as an aesthetic interpretation of a bat's perception, but also as an actual means of navigating through space. The sonar sensors are translated into an arpeggiator that intensifies at each panoramic position to give a sense of distance to the perceived obstacle. At the same time, the gyroscope modulates the harmonic relationship of the arpeggiator. The harmonies of the arpeggiator are also modulated by the gyroscope.

In addition, cluster chords without clear fundamental frequencies are randomly generated to contrast the harmony. They are triggered at a distance of 5 meters, while the arpeggiator starts at a distance of 3 meters. The cluster chords are positioned in the stereo panorama relative to magnetic north to reflect the bat's magnetic sense.

Finally, a synthetic piano generates chords in the range of Dmaj7, Dmmaj7, Dmin7, D0 and the same chords on the fifth (A). The voicings, velocity and timing of the notes are also randomized and spread over several octaves to create random melodies. These chords are triggered by acceleration and thus movement through space.

Overall, the musical composition is a mixture of dissonant, consonant and atonal layers. The piano gives a certain film noir feeling, while the cluster chords darken this impression even more. The arpeggiator clarifies these harmonies depending on the overall position of the listener. This is my personal idea of a bat on the hunt, flying through the night.

Fig. 3. The Bat-Headset (previous version) at NEW NOW 2023, Essen, Germany

4. WHAT IS IT (NOT) LIKE TO BE A BAT?

Do we now know better what it is like to be a bat? I would like to leave this question open and invite anyone interested to find out for themselves. However, we certainly cannot access a bat's subjective view and any interpretation has nothing to do with a bat's mind. However, we can get a different sense of space and use music as a means of navigation that forces us to explore and adapt to these new senses. The work is not a representation, but a manifestation of how media expands our senses, while it cannot turn us into someone else.

When I presented this work at the NEW NOW Festival at the Zeche Zollverein in Essen, Germany in June 2023, I received constructive feedback from users and had interesting discussions about technology and consciousness (Fig. 3). Some needed up to 15 minutes or more to explore the space and get familiar with the sounds and their modulation. Children in particular were quick to adapt. However, the headset is still fragile and had to be repaired after one day of use, for which I plan to make relevant improvements.

The current version is the fourth iteration of the headset. For the next version, I will redesign the entire headset while maintaining the essence of the current aesthetic. I will also be adding a light sensor that can distinguish between light,

dark and basic colors to modulate the sound even more. Additionally, the headset will get an ESP32 to be able to communicate with other headsets.

In the future, the focus will shift more to intersubjectivity. The main aspect of this project is the exploration of consciousness not only as an individual experience, but also as a shared phenomenon. By creating multiple headsets and inviting other artists to contribute their musical interpretations, the project aims to delve into the realm of shared experience and interaction. These headsets will also be able to modulate each other. This expansion into intersubjectivity seeks to illuminate how, despite the inaccessibility of another's consciousness, we can find common ground in shared perceptions and emotions, thereby enriching our understanding of both individual and collective experience.

In conclusion, while the question of what it is like to be a bat necessarily remains unanswered, the work serves as a contemporary example of what technology enables, as well as its limitations, in the exploration of individual and shared consciousness. It invites users to engage with space, sound, and their own beliefs, pushing the boundaries of perception and understanding in an ongoing quest. Nagel's argument reveals the limits of the human imagination, while the work harnesses the power of that ability to point to the unimaginable and define their boarder. With this artistic interpretation of a philosophical standpoint, I want to extend the debate to immediate and aesthetic experience, arguing for its irreducibility and independent meaning.

5. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/912907360?share=copy>

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

This work did not involve any living bats. All software is open source and the parts are publicly available. The project was self-funded. s

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Nagel, *What Is It Like to Be a Bat?*. Durham, NC, USA: The Philosophical Review, Vol. 83, No. 4 (Oct., 1974), pp. 435-450, 1974.